

A MODEL FOR ENSURING THE SAFETY OF PERSONNEL OPERATING IN UNDERGROUND MINES USING THE LINEAR EXTRAPOLATION METHOD

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Annotation: the mining industry is one of the most technologically complex and dangerous areas of activity, in which the safety of employees plays an important role. In this article, we will consider approaches to mathematical modeling based on extrapolation analysis of personnel safety in underground mines, which is a modern means of efficiently managing risks and ensuring labor safety. Assessment and security in the mining industry is an important task that requires a comprehensive approach. The article examines various mathematical modeling methods aimed at extrapolating current safety indicators to analyze them and predict future events. The study involves the development of mathematical models taking into account various factors affecting employee safety in mines.

Keywords: prediction, safety data, extrapolation, Occupational Safety, mathematical model, risk assessment in mines, random risks.

Introduction. Predicting process progress in the 21st century information technology age research has been one of the main tools of the process [1,2]. Extrapolation methods are common among all methods of prediction and are one of the most developed. When forming forecasts using the extrapolation method, usually changes in the quantitative characteristics of the object arise from statistically evolving trends [3].

The extrapolation method is used when the following situations are used:

- a) the time at which the function is constructed must be sufficient to determine the trend of development;
- b) the process being analyzed has a stable dynamic and inertia, that is, it takes time for a significant change in the characteristics of the process.

The extrapolation method is based on the study of the forecasting object, a retrospective analysis of quantitative time series or trends [4,5].

In mathematics and statistics, the extrapolation method is seen as one of the types of approximation that approximates this function outside a given interval, rather than between given values [6-8]. An analysis-based mathematical model using the extrapolation method of predicting employee safety in underground mines involves accounting for prior data and trends to predict future risk-related events [9-11].

Linear extrapolation, polynomial extrapolation, and exponential extrapolation allow the creation of complex mathematical models capable of analyzing and predicting employee safety in various phenomena using approaches [12-17].

The developed models allow current trends to be extrapolated and warned against potential risks, an important tool for effective safety measures in underground mines [18,19].

For the construction of this model, let us give information about the initial variables: let D_t be a set of security data in t -time, including a set of past events, equipment maintenance, inspections and other related factors. Then

$$D'_{t+1} = f(D_t).$$

where D'_{t+1} is the function predicting the future security situation on the basis of the D_t – of the cell? Let f be the set of factors that affect the safety of the circuit. A function that determines the security level $(S_{t_1}, S_{t_2}, \dots, S_{t_n})$ based on predicted data D'_{t+1} and influencing factors $(F_1, F_2, \dots, F_n)$ is given in the following (1) formula [20,22].

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} S_{t_1} = g(D'_{t_1}, F_1) \\ S_{t_2} = g(D'_{t_2}, F_2) \\ \vdots \\ S_{t_n} = g(D'_{t_n}, F_n) \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

$P_{bh_1}, P_{bh_2}, \dots, P_{bh_n}$ – let the clock be a function that determines the likelihood of emergency situations on the basis of the level of risk and other factors. Then this function becomes.

$$\begin{cases} P_{bh_1} = h(S_{t_1}, L_1) \\ P_{bh_2} = h(S_{t_2}, L_2) \\ \vdots \\ P_{bh_n} = h(S_{t_n}, L_n) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $L_1, L_2, \dots, L_n$ is the set of other factors.

Such a model provides a means of predicting risk levels based on previous data and allows for Trend Analysis, weak points detection, and measures to improve employee safety in underground mines.

Conclusion. Analysis of personnel safety in underground mines using the extrapolation method is an important modeling tool for the developing mining industry. This approach provides a systematic and accurate approach to predicting risks and developing strategies for ensuring labor security. Further research in this area will be a supportive system to improve existing models and provide a high level of security in underground mines. Imaging in underground mines using the extrapolation analysis method of mathematical modeling of employee safety provides an effective tool for predicting future safety events based on previous data and trends. The Model takes into account many factors affecting safety, including the technical condition of the equipment, the intensity of seismic activity and other variables. It allows you to regularly update, fix and adapt the model parameters based on new data to changing conditions. Thus, extrapolation can be used as a means of determining future expected values based on available information about trends in past changes.

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